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APL Photonics 11, 020802 (2026)

<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0282151>

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Cite as: APL Photon. 11, 020802 (2026); doi: 10.1063/5.0282151

Submitted: 23 May 2025 • Accepted: 19 January 2026 •

Published Online: 17 February 2026

View Online

Export Citation

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ABSTRACT

Photonic devices greatly benefit from the ability to reconfigure their optical properties. To achieve this with disordered optical materials, it is possible to make use of polymer dispersed liquid crystals (PDLCs) in which the scattering originates from randomly distributed liquid crystal droplets that respond to external stimuli, such as light, temperature, and magnetic or electric fields. In this work, we present a speckle-based analysis to investigate the reconfigurability of the dynamic and static scattering properties of dye-doped PDLCs, as a function of dye concentration and light intensity. Our findings allow us to distinguish between reversible and non-reversible molecular rearrangements after a light-induced phase transition, occurring on millisecond timescale. The degree of reversibility is quantified using cross-correlation analysis based on the Pearson correlation coefficient. As a proof-of-concept application, we exploit their non-reversible reconfiguration properties to create a cryptographic optical physical unclonable function whose behavior can progressively be erased in case of malicious attacks. We demonstrate a non-reversibility, assessed through the uniqueness metric, that ranges from 30% to 40% depending on dye content. Leveraging their intensity-dependent scattering properties, these disordered materials emerge as ideal candidates for advanced nonlinear information processing and secret-free security applications.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Complex photonic media, when illuminated by coherent light, cause the incident beam to diffuse into multiple random directions, resulting in the accumulation of diverse random phase delays determined by the optical path.^{1,2} The interference of scattered light forms in the far-field a speckle pattern that encodes information about the material properties.³ The intrinsic high sensitivity of this speckle pattern to small perturbations of the sample (down to the

single scattering center⁴), the surrounding environment,^{5–7} and the illuminating light⁸ enables to measure a wide range of physical quantities, a domain termed speckle metrology.⁹ Variations in the speckle pattern serve as a basis for measuring observables such as temperature, vibrations, and the morphological or optical properties of the scattering system.^{6,7,10,11} The non-invasive nature of this technique has found applications in biomedical research^{12,13} for *in vivo* physiological monitoring and in soft matter physics^{14–16} as a probe of heterogeneous dynamic behavior. In these fields, the properties of the

scattering medium become crucial, especially when the microscopic structure of complex materials can be deterministically modified by appropriate external stimuli.^{17–19} During reconfiguration processes, even minor internal material changes induce phase delay variations, resulting in alterations of transmitted and reflected speckle patterns. Leveraging this phenomenon, we employed the scattering process within light-reconfigurable materials to monitor and study their reconfiguration.

Reconfigurability is a crucial attribute for advanced tunable photonic systems. The ability to dynamically modulate material optical properties, such as refractive index, birefringence, or geometric features through an external stimulus, enables on-demand control of photonic functionalities, such as cavity resonances, photonic bandgaps, and interference effects.^{17,20–27} In particular, regarding disordered materials, it has been recently demonstrated that tunable scattering potential (i.e., a scalar tensor representing the 3D modulation of dielectric permittivity) allows for nonlinear optical mapping in a complex multiple-scattering cavity.²⁸ This new functionality opens up for new avenues, allowing for nonlinear optical PUFs,^{29–31} nonlinear optical encoding, and processing enabled by recurrent linear scattering.^{32,33} A wide range of responsive materials, including phase change materials, liquid crystals, and nonlinear materials, have been explored for reconfigurable photonics. Among these, liquid crystals (LCs) have found widespread use due to their self-organizing nature and reversible phase transitions, which are accompanied by significant refractive index variations.^{34–37} Although the inherent fluid nature of LCs might present challenges for integration and long-term stability, polymer-based LC formulations offer viable solutions. These include polymer-stabilized liquid crystals (PSLCs),³⁸ polymer-dispersed liquid crystals (PDLCs),^{39,40} and liquid crystal elastomers,⁴¹ which effectively preserve the optical properties of LCs within stable polymeric matrices. Furthermore, LC polymers facilitate the microdesigning of both the shape and optical properties of ordered and disordered photonic systems. Among these categories, PDLCs are obtained by a phase separation process resulting in a random dispersion of liquid crystal droplets in a polymeric matrix. Combining both the optical properties of the liquid crystal and the mechanical ones (such as elasticity, toughness, and strength) of the polymer, they have been widely applied for several applications that include smart windows,^{42,43} display technologies,⁴⁴ sensing,⁴⁵ and light modulation.⁴⁶ When using thermotropic liquid crystals, the introduction of dopants allows us to drive the liquid crystal to isotropic phase transition by light, thus exploiting the thermo-optic effect. By adjusting the liquid crystal-based polymer formulation, it is possible to obtain non-reversible systems, here referred to as reconfigurable,⁴⁷ and reversible systems, also known as switchable.⁴⁸

The scattering properties of disordered liquid crystal polymers have been investigated using speckle correlation in PSLCs to tailor scattering statistics⁴⁹ and dynamic light scattering in PDLCs under varying voltages.⁵⁰ Although speckle statistics have been manipulated in PSLCs to achieve different scattering regimes,⁴⁹ the reconfiguration process of PDLCs has not been previously explored through statistical speckle analysis.

In this work, we demonstrate both reversible and non-reversible reconfiguration processes in PDLCs via statistical and information-theoretical analysis of speckle patterns. We use a speckle-based approach, studying both the static and dynamic

statistical properties of the speckle pattern both under *local* and *non-local* illumination conditions. Here, we refer to *local* illumination as the condition where both interrogation and reconfiguration spots are focused onto the sample surface through a microscope objective. The focal spot has an area of a $1\text{--}5\ \mu\text{m}^2$ that is comparable to the average size of the scatterers (liquid crystal droplets). On the other hand, we name as *non-local* the illumination condition in which the interrogation and reconfiguration sources are imaged on the sample surface over an area of $1\ \text{cm}^2$. Speckle pattern similarity is studied via the widely used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) approach. In parallel, we employed a more information-theoretic approach (the Hamming distance), based on the degree of similarity of binary keys generated by the speckle diffraction patterns. As a third method, we used digital holography to reconstruct the speckle pattern scattered through the PDLC, from which we retrieved the phase variation of the generated speckles as an effect of the microscopic variation induced by the reconfiguration stimulus. The nematic to isotropic phase transition is finally assessed by Polarization Optical Microscope (POM) observations

Following these different approaches, we demonstrate that, in differently dye-doped PDLC systems under varying light intensities, the molecular alignment or the nematic-to-isotropic phase transition induces either a reversible or non-reversible refractive index change. Going beyond the reversible tuning reported in polymer dispersed and stabilized liquid crystals,⁴⁸ the light-induced reconfiguration allows for a gradual modification of the system's equivalent transfer matrix, offering a versatile approach to control its scattering potential. Despite the characterization and the methodology used to characterize PDLCs, both under *local* and *non-local* illumination conditions, the reconfigurability of our materials is of fundamental importance for a wide variety of applications.^{28,51–55} Among them, complex photonic systems have emerged as physical primitives for optical reconfigurable physical unclonable functions or PUFs. Optical PUFs, which rely on the intrinsic disorder of photonic complex systems, generate secure cryptographic keys upon coherent light interrogation.^{8,30,56–58} Although no physical law forbids the duplication of a classical system, we assume that the three-dimensional disordered materials considered here cannot be physically cloned given the current technological limitations and inadequate computational power, which prevent the replication or simulation of such 3D systems. Even if non-invasive attacks based on mathematical modeling such as machine learning have been successfully performed on different types of PUFs,^{59–62} mainly electronic ones, at present, a systematic study demonstrating the vulnerability of strong optical PUFs is still missing. The “technological protection” together with the mathematical modeling resilience make these classes of disordered photonics systems practically unclonable to date.

When the scattering properties of these systems are static, different challenge–response pairs (CRPs) can be generated by changing the interrogation condition (angle of incidence, polarization, and light phase modulation). This also applies to dye-doped PDLCs, in which the interaction of various interrogation wavefronts (plane waves or intensity/phase modulated beams) with the scatterers produces speckle patterns with high entropy due to the numerous degrees of freedom probed by scattered light.^{47,48} Moreover, the latter offer a dynamic change in the optical properties of the hardware itself by light exploiting the thermo-optic effect. Herein, we show that by simply adjusting the dye concentration, and the

intensity of the reconfiguration light source, the optical transfer function of the scattering media can be perturbed in a reversible and non-reversible way, thus creating correlated or uncorrelated responses, respectively, from the initial hardware. This procedure, easily triggered by light, opens up several scenarios behind the typical use of static scattering systems, including the development of reconfigurable optical PUF here proposed, for which the reconfiguration occurs in a non-reversible way. Such devices ensure the generation of a new PUF in case of malicious attacks with an unpredictable ability to generate different CRPs.⁶³ Moreover, reversible switching among different microscopic configurations can be explored for PUF secured quantum-readout methods, such as the proposed quantum secure authentication of classical data or quantum secure authentication of quantum data^{64,65} other than their possible applicability in structural nonlinearity.²⁸

II. SAMPLE FABRICATION, MICROSCOPIC ANALYSIS, AND SCATTERING PROPERTIES

Dye-doped polymer dispersed liquid crystal composites are prepared by first dissolving the azo-dye DR1 (Disperse Red 1) at different concentrations (1%, 3%, and 6% w/w) in the mesogen 5CB (4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl). Then, the dye-doped liquid crystal mixtures are blended with the PDMS pre-polymer (polydimethylsiloxane) in such quantities to have a final composition equal to 5% (w/w) of dye-doped LC and 95% (w/w) of PDMS. We refer to PDLC samples as 1% DR1, 3% DR1, and 6% DR1 according to the dye concentration in the liquid crystal mixture. A photograph of the three samples is reported in Fig. 1(a), and the complete sample fabrication procedure is described in Sec. I of the

supplementary material. Liquid crystal droplet formation and their radial alignment were both confirmed by polarized optical microscope observations (POM, Axiolab 5—POL—Zeiss) [Figs. 1(b) and 1(c) and the supplementary material]. The presence of black crosses inside the LC droplets proves that molecules are radially aligned [schematically reported in Fig. 1(d)].⁶⁶ Since polymerization is thermally induced, increasing the dye concentration does not affect the morphology of the sample and, in particular, the size of the droplets [Fig. 1(e)], whose diameter is around 5–6 μm . On the contrary, it affects both the order parameter and the nematic–isotropic transition temperature (T_{N-I}) of the dye-doped LC mixtures, both of which decrease with increasing dye concentration (see Figs. S1 and S2 of the supplementary material).

The scattering properties of the presented dye doped PDLCs, as well as their absorbance and transmittance, are assessed using integrating sphere based measurements both for interrogation (red) and reconfiguration (blue) light. The methodology used to determine the absorption l_a , transport l_t , and effective l_{eff} attenuation lengths is detailed in Sec. IV (supplementary material). The absorption length l_a of blue light decreases with increasing dye concentration, although it remains longer than the sample thickness ($L \approx 180 \mu\text{m}$) within the tested range. The transport mean free path l_t , at the interrogation wavelength, is a fraction of the thickness L of the sample ($L/l_t \approx 1-2$), values for which we reasonably assume that these samples fall within the single (or intermediate) scattering regime. The effective length, l_{eff} , is defined as the geometric mean of the absorption length and transport mean free path taking into account the dimensionality of the physical system. It provides the characteristic length after which the transmitted light is decreased by a factor $\frac{1}{e}$ when both scattering and absorption influence light propagation. For the considered samples, the effective length is shorter than the sample thickness at 468 nm.

FIG. 1. Material characterization. (a) A photograph of samples containing different amounts of DR1: higher dye concentration makes PDLCs appear darker red and less transparent. [(b) and (c)] PDLC observed by POM with a $5\times$ objective (b) and a $40\times$ objective (c). The black cross inside the droplets is related to the molecule alignment along the polarization direction of both polarizers. The inset of (c) shows the alignment direction of molecules inside the droplets and the direction of the polarizers. (d) Graphical representation of molecule arrangement inside the droplets. The radial organization is responsible for the “flower like” structure visible via POM. (e) Droplet diameter distribution evaluated by collecting ten different frames per sample corresponding to different zones with a $40\times$ objective. The average is obtained from the analysis of 250 droplets per sample. No significant dependence on dye concentration is observed.

III. METHODS AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUPS FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF SPECKLE SIMILARITIES

The interaction of liquid crystal droplets with a coherent light source causes scattering phenomena, ultimately resulting in speckle pattern formation [Fig. 2(a)]. The reconfiguration of these complex photonic systems is optically induced by a blue laser (450 nm), exploiting the thermo-optic effect of the dye molecules, which absorb at that wavelength. Because speckle is highly sensitive to the material's structure, even slight variations in the molecular arrangement lead to measurable speckle pattern changes. In this section, we describe the methods used to characterize the three PDLC formulations (1% DR1, 3% DR1, and 6% DR1), under two different illumination conditions, here named as *local* and *non-local*. Samples are characterized by monitoring the degree of similarity between the speckles generated with and without the reconfiguration laser beam at different blue light intensities, thereby exploring different reconfiguration regimes: reversible and non-reversible.

A. Pearson correlation coefficient to characterize linear speckle correlations

The Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) is a metric that quantifies the degree of linear correlation between two datasets, here corresponding to the raw speckle patterns. A PCC value close to 0

indicates the absence of linear correlation, and consequently significant differences between the speckle patterns, while a value close to 1 indicates strong linear correlation and similarity between them.

Therefore, the PCC is a measure of similarity between speckle patterns, whose variations in this work ultimately result from changes occurring within the material under fixed illumination conditions. This interpretation is supported by POM observations performed under similar illumination conditions.

The PCC is computed between speckle patterns acquired both before and after, and before and during, the reconfiguration process. When the PCC is calculated from speckle patterns recorded before and after reconfiguration, it evaluates the degree of reversibility, indicating whether the reconfiguration has occurred reversibly or not. We define as reversible a reconfiguration that yields a PCC value in the range 1.0–0.8, while we consider it non-reversible when PCC falls within the range 0.5–0.3, or even lower. Such a system is also defined as reconfigurable. When the PCC is computed between the speckle patterns generated before and during a reconfiguration process, it can indicate, when combined with further characterization, whether the system has undergone a phase transition or a molecular rearrangement. Moreover, by tracking the temporal evolution of the PCC, it is possible to monitor the dynamics of the reconfiguration process. This is represented through correlation matrices, which report the correlation coefficients between speckle

FIG. 2. Principle of speckle pattern formation, methods for similarity analysis, and experimental set-up. (a) The system under investigation is illuminated with a spatially modulated wavefront that after the interaction with the medium generates the speckle pattern. A second source (blue light) is used to reconfigure the system. (b) The speckle pattern similarity is evaluated via three different methods: correlation matrix between raw speckle intensity images, fractional Hamming distance between binarized speckle intensity images, and phase delay measured with digital holography. (c) Setup used for the *local* characterization of PDLC systems. The He–Ne laser is the interrogation source, while the diode laser is the reconfiguration one. The optical components are linear polarizer (P), lenses (L), spatial light modulator (SLM), dichroic mirror (DM), and digital micro-mirror device (DMD). The camera is equipped with a blue light filter to avoid reconfiguration light source collection. The clock cartoon shows the temporal sequence for the interrogation and reconfiguration. The OFF state refers to the interrogation of sample with the He–Ne laser only. The liquid crystals are in the nematic phase. Once the reconfiguration light source is switched ON, molecules reach the isotropic phase, and the speckle patterns change.

patterns acquired at different times [Fig. 2(b)] along multiple reconfiguration cycles. The ON–OFF alternation of the reconfiguration light along the cycle determines similar PCC values in the correlation matrix, which appears as “squares” in the left panel of Fig. 2(b). The squares along the diagonal correspond to the correlations of the speckles within the same configuration (ON, when blue light is on; OFF, when it is off), while adjacent squares refer to the cross-correlations between speckles generated under different configurations.

B. Hamming distance between binary keys generated by different speckles

The Hamming distance (HD) is a metric derived from information theory and commonly used in cryptography that measures the difference between two keys of equal length by counting the number of symbols that differ. When normalized to the total length of the strings, the resulting metric is the fractional Hamming distance (FHD), which ranges between 0 and 1. In the context of optical PUFs, cryptographic keys are extracted from sets of different optical responses to multiple challenges (intensity, or phase, modulated light patterns). The FHD is computed on these responses, specifically on the post-processed (e.g., Gabor-filtered) and binarized speckle patterns.⁵⁶ On the contrary, PCC is directly computed from raw speckle patterns. Three different types of FHD are typically evaluated: the *like*, the *unlike*, and the *inter-like*. The *like* FHD is calculated by comparing responses generated by the same PUF to the same set of challenges. Generally, this distribution has a bell-like shape and is centered between 0.01 and 0.1, indicating the reliability of the system. In contrast, the *unlike* FHD is computed between responses to different challenges extracted from the same PUF. The desirable values of *unlike* are distributed around 0.5, indicating good bit uniformity; from the width of the distribution, it is also possible to estimate the system’s entropy (see Sec. V C for details). The separation and possible overlap between *like* and *unlike* distributions provide information about the degree of similarity of the binarized speckle patterns [see Fig. 2(b)].

In this work, the *inter-like* FHD (iFHD) is the distribution of distances between responses obtained from the same PUF interrogated with the same set of challenges before and after a reconfiguration process. This distribution indicates the uniqueness of the non-reversibly reconfigured PUF and, thus, its reconfigurability. *Inter-like* FHD values close to 0.5 (uniqueness = 50%) indicate that reconfiguration has occurred in a non-reversible way.

C. Digital holography to measure temporal evolution of the speckle phase

The third method used to assess the effect of PDLC reconfiguration induced by an external light stimulus is based on digital holography. As an interferometric technique, it enables the numerical reconstruction of the optical wavefront in terms of its amplitude and phase components, which contain information of the illuminated sample. Here, we monitor the time evolution of the phase of the scattered field to gain insight into the phase delay induced by the sample under different reconfiguration light intensities.

D. Experimental setups

Figure 2(c) shows the schematic of the experimental setup, which comprises the interrogation source, a He–Ne laser (Thorlabs—HRP050, 632.8 nm, 5 mW) and the reconfiguration source, a diode laser with tunable power (CNI Optoelectronics—MDL-III-450, 450 nm, 500 mW). This setup has been used for both the PCC and the FHD distribution analysis. The He–Ne laser beam passes through a linear polarizer and a beam expander before illuminating the spatial light modulator (SLM), which operates in the phase-only configuration to generate the challenges. The phase-modulated beam (the challenge) is then coupled to an optical objective, and the sample is placed at the focal plane. Both light sources are focused on the sample through the same objective (Nikon, 20×, NA = 0.5), and the speckle patterns are collected using a second objective (Nikon, 40×, NA = 0.75). The illumination spots of both light sources have approximately an area equal to $1 \mu\text{m}^2$ – $5 \mu\text{m}^2$ on the sample surface. A CCD camera (iXon Ultra 897—Andor) records the speckle patterns within a region of 256×256 pixels. The camera is equipped with a linear polarizer with the fast axis orthogonal to the polarization of the input challenges and a longpass filter. These optical components allow us to filter out ballistic light and block blue light while transmitting the speckle pattern generated by the red challenge only. For dynamic analysis, the reconfiguration beam is switched ON and OFF by the digital micromirror device (DMD) at regular intervals of 5 s, while the red light remains ON throughout the entire measurement. The reconfiguration cycle is illustrated in the inset of Fig. 2(c): 5 s of red light illumination with a fixed challenge (OFF state), followed by 5 s of blue light exposure to enable reconfiguration (ON state), during which both light sources are activated. A total of six reconfiguration cycles (60 s) are recorded continuously for each sample.

For the holographic method, a different setup is used, based on a standard Mach–Zehnder-like holographic interferometer (see Sec. VI of the [supplementary material](#) for a detailed description). A solid state continuous wave laser (532 nm) is used for illumination. The light scattered by the PDLC represents the object wave, and it interferes with the so-called reference wave to form a hologram collected by the camera. This hologram allows us to digitally reconstruct the phase and amplitude of the scattered field at any given distance from the sample surface (Fig. S5 of the [supplementary material](#)). By calculating the argument of the scattered wave, a phase image of the speckle pattern is obtained. Since the green laser also acts as the reconfiguration stimulus, the temporal evolution of the phase can be retrieved through a sequential acquisition of the holograms.

IV. SIMILARITY OF SPECKLES GENERATED BY DIFFERENT MATERIAL CONFIGURATIONS

In this section, we present the results of the speckle similarity analysis obtained with the PCC method and the digital holographic technique. The results are discussed in relation to the effect of dye concentration and reconfiguration light power. The information-theoretic approach based on FHD is presented in the final section, where we propose a class of optically reconfigurable complex systems that could be implemented in practice.

A. Dependence of reconfiguration efficiency on dye concentration and activation laser power

The temporal evolution of the speckle patterns scattered by the PDLCs during the reconfiguration cycles is studied using PCC analysis. Figure 3(a) shows the correlation matrices of raw speckle pattern intensities from two consecutive reconfiguration cycles. For each sample, three different blue light powers (4, 14, and 25 mW) are used to induce reconfiguration. The cross-correlation between the speckle patterns obtained after consecutive reconfigurations clearly depends on the dye concentration and on the power of the reconfiguration source.

Figure 3(b) shows the PCC values computed at increasing reconfiguration light power. Samples with 1% and 3% of DR1 exhibit a reversible reconfiguration behavior at low powers. In fact, below 14 mW (1%) and 4 mW (3%), the PCC values between speckle patterns corresponding to consecutive OFF states (OFF_n-OFF_{n+1}) and between consecutive OFF and ON states (OFF_n-ON_n) remain close to 1. To understand the physical mechanism under this reversible

behavior that is not expected for PDLCs, we study single LC droplets under blue reconfiguration at POM (see Figs. S8–S11 of the [supplementary material](#)). By using comparable light intensities of the speckle pattern analysis, we find out two different behaviors: at low dye concentrations and under blue light illumination at low power, the droplet undergoes a LC rotation with a partial disordering without becoming fully isotropic (dark) and it is able to recover the initial alignment; while when increasing the power, the droplet reaches the isotropic state (fully dark) and the alignment is not recovered anymore. Most likely, it is a partial molecular rearrangement that leads to the switchable behavior already observed in PDLCs under electro-optical effect.^{50,67} On the other hand, the 6% DR1 PDLC sample fails to recover its initial configuration, even at low blue light power, suggesting that reconfiguration occurs non-reversibly.

When considering the minimum PCC values reached by each sample for the OFF_n-ON_n comparison, no notable differences are observed. This suggests that, above the power threshold,

FIG. 3. Speckle-based analysis of reconfiguration process dynamics. (a) Correlation matrices start from OFF state. The squares on the diagonal correspond to the auto-correlation, where values come from correlation between every speckle pattern of the same state. The presence of yellow squares suggests PCC values close to one, indicating great similarity between speckle patterns, while the blue squares indicate PCC values close to 0. The color bar applies to all matrices. (b) PCC values calculated by comparing the last frame of two consecutive OFF states (OFF_n-OFF_{n+1}) and by comparing the last frame of consecutive OFF and ON states (OFF_n-ON_n). The values are reported as a mean of six different reconfiguration cycles along with their standard deviation. (c) Temporal evolution of the Pearson correlation coefficient. The profile comes from plotting the PCC values in correspondence of the last OFF frame.

the nematic-to-isotropic phase transition occurs in the entire LC droplet. These evidences together with the POM analysis support that the reversible or non-reversible reconfiguration within the droplet depends on the partial or complete LC rearrangement.

At increasing reconfiguration powers, a consistent trend is observed across all samples, independent of dye content. Once each sample reaches the threshold required to induce reconfiguration (i.e., the low PCC value obtained for the $\text{OFF}_n\text{-OFF}_{n+1}$), which is specific for each dye content, further increases in the reconfiguration light power do not lead to additional improvements in reconfiguration.

Figure 3(c) shows the temporal evolution of the PCC values across six consecutive reconfiguration cycles. These profiles are extracted from the correlation matrices [Fig. 3(a)] using the last frame (speckle pattern) of the first OFF state as a reference. The PCC values are computed by comparing this reference with preceding and subsequent frames. During the ON states, the PCC values decrease as the liquid crystal molecules undergo either molecular reorientation (at low intensity) or the nematic-to-isotropic phase transition (at high intensity). This drop in PCC values, observed when passing from OFF to ON, is referred to as *decay*. The PCC values of different OFF states remain nearly constant over time, indicating the absence of any memory effect between consecutive cycles. As already observed, an increase in both dye concentration and reconfiguration power leads to lower correlation values between subsequent OFF states and the first one.

When analyzing the *decay* profile, a steeper PCC variation is observed for each sample with increasing power, suggesting a faster dynamic of the nematic-to-isotropic phase transition. The higher reconfigurability and faster response for the 6% DR1 sample are attributed to its greater absorbance and lower transition temperature (see Figs. S2 and S3 of the [supplementary material](#)), which allow a larger region of the sample to undergo the phase transition, thus reconfiguring the whole 3-D volume responsible for the speckle pattern. In contrast, at low intensities, the lower dye content in the 1% and 3% DR1 samples does not allow for a complete nematic-to-isotropic phase transition throughout the volume but only triggers a molecular rearrangement, ultimately reducing the reconfigurability of these systems due to their higher transition temperature. Therefore, by tuning the dye content and the power of the blue light, PDLCs exhibit both the reversible and non-reversible reconfiguration of the optical transfer matrix.

We study the decorrelation of the speckle as a function of the polarization state of the interrogation beam. We characterize the 6% DR1 sample for the two input polarization states (H, horizontal, and V, vertical) and in two illumination-collection channels, the parallel (HH or VV) and the cross (HV or VH) channels. We observe that the degree of correlation between consecutive OFF states depends on the illumination-collection channel (parallel or crossed) for which the contribution of ballistic light is substantially different but does not depend on the absolute state of input polarization of the interrogation beam (see Sec. V and Fig. S4 of the [supplementary material](#)).

On the other hand, we verify the independence of the speckle pattern decorrelation with respect to the polarization state of the interrogation beam that can be ascribed to the isotropic scattering properties of the material. There is no impact of the polarization of

the reconfiguration beam on the degree of reconfigurability (see Sec. V of the [supplementary material](#)).

B. Speckle correlation and speckle phase variation from digital holography analysis

In this subsection, we compare PCC speckle analysis with the phase change in the speckle pattern during the reconfiguration process in the 1% DR1 sample. Digital holography measurements allow us to gain new insight into the reconfiguration process by directly quantifying the average phase variation of the speckle scattered by the sample. At the same time, it is possible to measure the speckle intensities to quantify the speckle similarities through the PCCs. Although DR1 exhibits comparable absorbance at 532 and 450 nm (see Sec. B and Fig. S1 of the [supplementary material](#)), a quantitative comparison of the power threshold shown in Fig. 3 is not feasible due to the different illumination conditions. Nonetheless, speckle holography analysis reveals a similar behavior with reversible and non-reversible reconfiguration. Figure 4(a) shows the PCC analysis at increasing power for the 1% DR1 sample. The cross-correlations between two consecutive measurements show different behaviors with increasing power. At low power (10 mW), the speckle patterns from consecutive measurements are highly correlated, while higher reconfiguration powers cause a completely different behavior. When the light power exceeds 35 mW, a decorrelation between the first and the second measurements is observed, resulting in a non-reversible reconfiguration of the system. The analysis of the phase variation during the switching/reconfiguration process is presented in Figs. 4(b) and 4(c). Panel b reports the amplitude of the speckle pattern obtained by numerically reconstructing the hologram, in which the dashed box indicates the region of interest (ROI) for the phase change analysis. The two insets show the reconstructed speckle amplitude at the beginning and end of the measurements. Figure 4(c) shows the median of the temporal phase evolution evaluated within the ROI for three laser powers. The rate of phase change and the asymptotic values of the accumulated phase depend on the illumination power. The continuous lines are the result of the fitting with the sum of two exponential functions. The rate of the fast process shows a modest increase with power, i.e., from $1/\tau = 2.3$ Hz at 10 mW, up to $1/\tau = 3.3$ Hz at 35 mW, while the slower process remains nearly constant. At the same time, the accumulated phase increases from 2.5 to 15 radians. As expected, this speckle reconfiguration is accompanied by a temperature variation with increasing illumination power (see Fig. S7 of the [supplementary material](#)). At low power, the average temperature variation on the surface of the sample is less than 0.5 °C, thus preventing a complete LC phase transition within the droplets that results in a very low phase change in the speckle pattern. By increasing the power, a larger average temperature difference is recorded possibly suggesting a local achievement of the temperature induced phase transition. Phase and temperature variation in PDLC indicates that, within the LC droplets, a variation of the material's refractive index occurs. However, since the material under examination is not homogeneous but rather a complex system in which the active scatterers are only a small percentage of the scattering volume, a proper model is required for a precise evaluation. The observed phase variation is compatible with an average refractive index change on the order of $\Delta n = 10^{-2}$, a reasonable value for these kinds of systems. A more

FIG. 4. Holography speckle patterns. (a) Correlation matrices obtained by computing the PCCs between two sets of speckle patterns recorded under green light illumination. The squares off the diagonal correspond to the linear correlation between the first and second measurements. (b) Amplitude image of the speckle pattern obtained by numerically reconstructing the hologram. The insets show the speckle pattern at the start of the interrogation ($t = 0$ s) and at the end of the interrogation ($t = 42$ s). (c) Temporal evolution of the phase change in the speckle pattern calculated as the median value within the dashed square shown in panel (b) for three different optical powers (10, 22, and 35 mW).

accurate investigation of the microscopic refractive index variation due to the phase changes in the speckle pattern will be the object of a future study.

Finally, the digital holography analysis shows that, during a reconfiguration cycle, the phase of the scattered field evolves over time, suggesting that light can modulate the optical response of reconfigurable disordered systems both in a reversible and non-reversible way.

V. POTENTIAL APPLICATION OF PDLC MATERIALS FOR A RECONFIGURABLE CRYPTO-KEY GENERATOR

Among the various applications of disordered reconfigurable photonic materials, we propose here the application of PDLCs for the realization of reconfigurable optical physical unclonable functions.^{47,54,55} PUFs are a class of cryptographic primitives used for on-demand generation of cryptographic keys. Such systems are able to provide unique *responses* when subjected to a certain stimulus interrogation, referred to as *challenges*.⁵⁶ The uniqueness of the response is strictly related to the material intrinsic disorder,

which results from the manufacturing process. PUFs can be classified according to the type of stimulus used to interrogate the system; among them, two main classes exist: electrical and optical PUFs.^{68,69}

Optical PUFs provide several advantages over the electrical ones, including greater complexity (and, thus, security), the possibility to exploit nonlinear phenomena, and a greater number of degrees of freedom of the interrogation source, such as light power, amplitude, and phase.⁵⁴ In optical PUFs, the interrogation is performed using a coherent light source, while the response is a speckle pattern. Proper filtering and binarization are needed to transform raw speckle patterns into cryptographic keys.⁵⁶ The random dispersion of LC droplets is strictly related to the manufacturing process and cannot be cloned or simulated with current technology, ultimately providing unclonability. Moreover, PDLCs' scattering properties and their tunability through the thermo-optic effect make these systems suitable for reconfigurable optical PUFs development. Such systems undergo irreversible changes when subjected to a reconfiguration stimulus, thereby generating a new PUF. The possibility to irreversibly reconfigure the token, and so to create a new PUF, enhances the security of the system in case of third-party attacks.⁶³

A. PUF-based authentication protocol

PUFs can be used in authentication protocols, whose schematic procedure is shown in Fig. 5(a). The process consists of three phases: enrollment, authentication, and verification. During the enrollment phase, the PUF is characterized by a trusted party (e.g., central authority). The PUF is interrogated with multiple challenges, and the corresponding responses are collected. A set of challenge–response pairs (CRPs) is then created and safely stored. The PUF is subsequently sent to the user, who will use it for authentication purposes. In the authentication phase, the verifier selects a CRP from the database and sends the corresponding challenge to the user, who interrogates the PUF and generates the response. This response is sent back to the verifier, who compares it with the one stored in the database. If the two responses match, the user is successfully authenticated (verification phase). Otherwise, the verifier can repeat the authentication phase with a different CRP. Each CRP must be used only once and deleted from the database after use.⁷⁰

B. Efficiency of reconfiguration evaluated with fractional Hamming distance

The applicability of PDLC systems for reconfigurable optical PUF development is evaluated by interrogating the three dye-doped PDLC samples with multiple challenges. A set of ten thousand

different challenges is used for this purpose and five reconfiguration cycles are performed. For this characterization, a slightly different setup from the one presented above is used [schematically shown in Fig. 5(b)]. To generate the challenges, the He–Ne laser beam impinges on the DMD, spatially modulating its amplitude. The resulting wavefronts are randomly modulated in amplitude, with 50% of the pixels turned on and 50% off. The random chessboard consists of 256×256 pixels. The size of the collimated challenge beam impinging on the sample is $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$, and the reconfiguration light source used is an LED projector that emits a collimated beam at 460 nm. The two illumination areas (blue and red light) completely overlap on the sample during the reconfiguration process. Each sample is interrogated with a set made of 10k ($\{1k + 9k\}$) different challenges, and the first 1k challenges are acquired twice ($\{1k + 9k\} + 1k$ total challenges) before reconfiguring the systems, to evaluate *like* FHD distributions (see subsection III B). The *unlike* FHD distribution is calculated by cross-comparing the 10k ($\{1k + 9k\}$) challenges [see Fig. 5(c)]. The FHD values are in good agreement with what was expected: the *like* distribution centered around 0.1 indicates good similarity between the cryptographic keys extracted by interrogating the PUF with the same set of challenges. In contrast, the *unlike* FHD distribution is centered around 0.5, indicating that, on average, two keys differ in 50% of the bits, as expected for two randomly generated keys. Furthermore, the large separation between the two distributions allows us to set the authentication

FIG. 5. PDLC-based PUFs. (a) PUF-based authentication process. The PUF is first produced and characterized. A database containing different challenge–response pairs (CRPs) is created and securely stored by the central authority. The device is then given to the user, who uses it for authentication purpose. (b) PDLC interrogation with challenges. The challenges generated by the DMD are projected onto the sample, producing speckle patterns recorded by the camera. The reconfiguration light is projected onto the sample, and the two spots (interrogation and reconfiguration) completely overlap. (c) *Like* and *unlike* FHD distributions for 1% DR1 sample, where no reconfiguration process has yet been performed. (d) *Inter-like* FHD distributions of the 1% DR1, 3% DR1, and 6% DR1 samples. Each distribution is obtained by comparing 10 000 different challenges, with a reconfiguration process performed between the two acquisitions. (e) Entropy values extracted from cryptographic keys generated by PUFs subjected to consecutive reconfiguration cycles. The entropy increases with the number of reconfiguration cycles. The inset shows the relative variation of entropy with respect to the case in which no reconfiguration is performed. For all samples, a clear trend is observed with increasing dye concentration.

threshold at FHD ≈ 0.3 . This indicates that the system, at least for the dataset considered here, composed of 10^4 responses, is reliable as a PUF implementation. The pairwise comparisons on which the *unlike* FHD is computed is $\frac{M^2-M}{2} \approx 10^7$, where M is the number of responses (10^4). It is reasonable to assume that the estimated overlap between the two curves, and consequently the probability of error in authentication, given the number of responses, is below 10^{-7} (false acceptance and false rejection rates). Similar distributions for the sample 3% DR1 and 6% DR1 are reported in Sec. IX and Fig. S12 of the [supplementary material](#).

Once the $\{1k + 9k\} + 1k$ total challenges are collected, the blue source is activated to reconfigure the sample, while the red interrogation is paused. A waiting period, during which neither the blue nor the red sources are on, ensures that the LC molecules have fully recovered their nematic phase. At the end of this time interval, the system is interrogated again with the same $\{1k + 9k\} + 1k$ set of challenges used previously. The reconfiguration period, the laser power used, and the waiting time needed by the system to relax to the nematic phase depend on challenge size. For each sample, six consecutive acquisitions are performed, with a reconfiguration process in between, and the *inter-like* FHD distributions are calculated. [Figure 5\(d\)](#) shows the *inter-like* FHD for the three investigated samples. The degree of the reconfiguration exhibits an opposite trend compared to the one observed with the previous characterization, where the interrogation is performed in a *local* regime, with both light beams focused. Under the *non-local* interrogation conditions, which correspond to an interrogation area of $\approx 1 \text{ cm}^2$, increasing dye concentration results in lower reconfiguration efficiency. The 6% DR1 sample shows an average *inter-like* FHD ≈ 0.29 , suggesting that the reconfiguration process is less efficient compared to the 3% DR1 (FHD ≈ 0.35) and 1% DR1 (FHD ≈ 0.42) samples. This opposite behavior can be explained by the different interrogation conditions. In the *non-local* regime, both the interrogation and reconfiguration areas are about 10^8 times larger than the *local* regime, resulting here in a much lower reconfiguration intensity. This implies that the intensity might be not sufficient to activate the LC phase transition all throughout the film with 6% DR1.

C. Entropy evaluation of the extracted cryptographic keys

Information entropy is a fundamental quantity that must be considered when evaluating the security level of cryptographic keys.⁷¹ The larger the entropy of a cryptographic key, the higher is the resilience against brute force attacks. The entropy of the keys is evaluated by assuming that the *unlike* FHD can be modeled as a Bernoulli trial $B(N, p)$, albeit with correlations between successive PUF responses.^{56,71} For large N values, the expected binomial distribution can be well approximated by a Gaussian, which makes it possible to estimate the number N of independent bits within the keys using the following equation:

$$N = \frac{p(1-p)}{\sigma^2}, \quad (1)$$

which is associated with the PUF entropy/information content. Here, p is the mean value of the distribution and σ is the standard deviation. The entropy values are calculated by randomly combining sets of 2.5k different responses extracted from PUFs generated after

one or multiple reconfiguration cycles. When considering a larger number of reconfiguration cycles, entropy rises. Since this effect is not observed when increasing the number of responses (see Sec. X of the [supplementary material](#)), independently from dye content, the raise can be attributed to the reconfiguration process, which enables the interrogation beam to probe a greater degree of freedom within samples. Each sample follows a similar trend, showing an increase in entropy when increasing the number of reconfiguration cycles [[Fig. 5\(e\)](#)], suggesting that the reconfiguration process increases the complexity and security of the cryptographic keys extracted.⁴⁸ The relative variation of entropy with respect to the case in which no reconfiguration is performed [inset of [Fig. 5\(e\)](#)] is greater for the lower dye concentration for which the reconfiguration is more efficient. Similar to what is observed for FHD distributions, PDLCs with higher DR1 concentration, characterized by a lower reconfiguration, have a lower net entropy increase.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we report a speckle-based statistical analysis on the light induced reconfiguration of polymer dispersed liquid crystal systems. The high sensitivity of speckle patterns allows us to detect minimal system variations, resulting in a powerful tool for evaluating both the degree of reconfigurability and the dynamics of the process. However, speckle pattern similarity does not provide insight into the underlying processes or mechanisms for which we provide a complementary characterization technique and analysis. By using three different methodologies, we show that the reconfiguration level can be effectively controlled by adjusting the dye concentration and the reconfiguration intensity of PDLCs. Furthermore, the speckle analysis together with an observation at the polarized optical microscope reveals that tuning these parameters enables two different operational regimes: reversible and non-reversible molecular rearrangement. In particular, at low dye content, the system undergoes a reversible molecular arrangement when illuminated with low intensities, as suggested by the high PCC values between speckle patterns acquired before and after reconfiguration. Under this condition, the system fully recovers the initial molecular orientation and exhibits a reversible behavior. Conversely, at higher dye content and/or higher illumination intensities, the reconfiguration is non-reversible, since the initial molecular organization is not completely restored even after the removal of the reconfiguration source. This light control over the reconfiguration properties of a PDLC opens up new applications in reconfigurable scattering media. The non-reversible reconfigurability of these systems was then exploited for reconfigurable optical PUFs. We demonstrate that by increasing the number of the reconfiguration cycles, the entropy of the extracted cryptographic keys increases, suggesting that the reconfiguration process plays a crucial role in enhancing systems' security. Overall, in PUF context, PDLCs provide a tailorable reconfiguration of the PUF hardware toward higher secure PUFs in case of third-party attack.⁶³

The custom PDLC formulation and the spatial control of the reconfiguration across different length scales provide a versatile, cheap, and easy to fabricate platform for advanced all-optical processing^{28,33} and secure authentication via quantum-readout protocols.^{64,65} Moreover, these hardware enriched with anisotropic scattering properties^{72,73} provide a versatile platform for PUFs with

enhanced security by polarization effects and fundamental studies on polarized light in mirror-symmetric disordered scattering media.⁷⁴

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The [supplementary material](#) contains the detailed description of sample fabrication and characterization, including the optical and thermal analyses of PDLC. Moreover, we discuss further the speckle analysis via interferometric measurements, polarized optical microscope evaluation, polarization dependence, and entropy analysis.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially supported by the project SERICS (No. PE00000014) under the MUR National Recovery and Resilience Plan funded by the European Union—NextGenerationEU—and co-funded by the European Union—NextGenerationEU, “Integrated infrastructure initiative in Photonic and Quantum Sciences”—I-PHOQS (Nos. IR0000016, ID D2B8D520, CUP B53C22001750006) and by Horizon WIDERA 2021-ACCESS-03-01 “BioQantSense” (No. 101079355). S.N. acknowledges the financial support from project “PRIN 2022 2022T3B4HS-PE11—Multi-step optical encoding in anticounterfeiting photonic tags based on liquid crystals (PHOTAG)” financed in the framework of Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR). F.R. acknowledges the financial support from the Air Force Office of Scientific Research under Award No. FA8655-24-1-7005. This work was also partially supported by the Ministry of Science, and Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia. We thank L. Pattelli and E. Pini for their help and discussion on the scattering properties analysis and V. Spinoso for the sample thickness measurements.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

S. Salvestrini: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **F. Maestri:** Investigation (supporting); Methodology (equal). **G. E. Lio:** Methodology (supporting); Software (lead). **F. Krajinic:** Investigation (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Writing – original draft (supporting). **S. Savic-Sevic:** Methodology (supporting). **B. Muric:** Methodology (supporting). **D. Pantelic:** Supervision (supporting). **B. Jelenkovic:** Supervision (supporting). **D. S. Wiersma:** Project administration (supporting); Resources (supporting); Supervision (supporting). **S. Nocentini:** Conceptualization (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **F. Riboli:** Conceptualization

(equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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